

CircularPSP: AI-Powered Platform for Advancing Urban Circular Economy Transitions

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Abstract—The CircularPSP project is developing an AI-powered Public Service Platform (PSP) to support municipalities in their transition to a circular economy (CE). Municipalities, which are responsible for significant resource consumption, face systemic barriers to adopting CE practices. Eight municipalities identified four main challenge areas: access to information, operations, organisation and change. A joint pre-commercial procurement (PCP) was initiated to stimulate the development of CE-solutions. These solutions integrate large language models (LLMs) trained on a curated CE Taxonomy with multilingual and contextual support. The core objective is to provide local government staff - regardless of their level of expertise - with useful workflows to enable day-to-day implementation of CE strategies, complemented by critical functionality for decision makers, CE experts and procurement officers. Testing will include real-world deployment across 20 local government organisations from 2025, with evaluation focused on user satisfaction and ability to achieve circular impact. The approach aims to produce scalable, transferable tools to support CE adoption in diverse local contexts across the EU.

Keywords — circular economy, AI, platform, city, urban, circular transition, sustainability, LLM, process

I. INTRODUCTION

Transitioning to a circular economy (CE) is essential to achieve climate neutrality and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1]. A local economy utilising CE is more resilient and improves strategic autonomy [2]. However, transition to a CE has recently begun to stall. Globally, circularity declined from 9.1% in 2018 to 7.2% in 2023 [3]. Urban areas are particularly sensitive to material flows representing 85% of GDP [4] and are responsible for 75% of the world's resource consumption [5]. In Europe, around 60% of public procurement (of €2 trillion per year) occur across 250,000 public organisations, of which many on local or regional level [6]. Although public procurement has been upheld as a powerful policy action to enhance resource efficiency in the economy by leveraging innovative and resource efficient solutions [7], the OECD [8] reported that only 10% of cities have advanced on circular transition and urban policies remain rooted in linear economic models [9].

Thus, the transition to CE is a wide-ranging systemic challenge which can be driven by many public organisations with significant buying power and leverage to change local economies. Currently, only few lighthouse cities have sufficient resources to integrate the growing number of vertical technologies [10] across sectoral

boundaries to overcome this compartmentalisation and to facilitate the transition to CE [11]. Such strategies are often neither scalable, nor directly transferrable to other cities [12]. Effective transfer of CE solutions is hindered by a combination of factors. First, it requires careful consideration of context-specific factors, including varying socio-cultural and geographical conditions [13]. Building upon this, knowledge sharing is hampered by the absence of universally agreed indicators and methodologies for measuring circularity [14]. Moreover, a considerable knowledge gap remains on how organisations can effectively integrate 4.0 technologies (e.g. Artificial Intelligence (AI)) which have been identified as key enablers of CE [15]. Crucially, these challenges are exacerbated by insufficient progress in making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) in the CE space, which has significant implications for peer-to-peer learning [16].

As part of the CircularPSP [17] project, eight leading municipalities, i.e. 'Procurers', (CircularBerlin, ReLondon, Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality, Forum Virium Helsinki, Guimarães, Sandyford Business District and National City Networks of Sweden and Slovenia) investigated the common challenges via a survey, focus groups and through market consultation. The group has identified four challenge areas: information, operation, organisation and change which required dedicated research and development.

The analysis led to a joint pre-commercial procurement of innovation (PCP) [18]. The common challenge shared between Procurers is outlined in a common Challenge Brief [19]. The guiding principle of the Brief is to design, develop and test an innovative 'circular economy solution' (CE-solution) that enables municipalities and their staff as well as businesses in the local economy to apply circular practice more quickly, frequently, widely and therefore overcome inefficiencies (e.g. research) and institutional (e.g. lack of coordination) and behavioural (e.g. perceived risks) barriers.

The PCP call for tenders received 15 applications [20], with five selected Suppliers competing through the PCP stages of which two remain as per April 2025. Real-life testing with procuring municipalities for both is expected to begin in the summer 2025 followed by limited public testing from autumn 2025 onwards.

The CE-solution deploys AI as part of a Public Service Platform (PSP) offering a city-wide view and process-

oriented guidance on circular action, taking the local framework condition as well personal knowledge and experience into account. The AI has been trained on a wide range of data sources including case studies, indicators and procurement criteria which have been collected in the open access document repository ‘CE Taxonomy’ [21]. The tools are to enable cities to communicate targets, support CE experts in interacting with municipal staff. Regular users are guided in their day-to-day work by ‘workflows’ enabling them to follow, upskill and implement increasingly ambitious circular action. Via the PSP, local businesses receive improved access to changing procurement needs, upskilling and funding. Overall, the CE-solution is to be highly scalable, secure and affordable so that thousands of public organisations can begin their transition regardless the starting point.

This paper first sets some background on the concept of CE, Pre-Commercial Procurement, and CE Taxonomy in section II, then describes the four core challenges in Section III which is subsequently followed by a generic description of the CE-solutions which have evolved during competition and co-design in Section IV. The upcoming real-life testing procedure and evaluation methodology is outlined in Section V which is then followed by the conclusion offered in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Circular Economy (CE)

CE in essence is an economy that aims to design out waste, keep products and materials in use, and regenerate natural systems [22]. Such a system is engineered for resource efficiency, product life extension, closed-loop systems, and reverse logistics [23]. Literature has not reached consensus on its working mechanisms [24], [25] and offer a variety of definitions [26] and indicators [27].

In the context of the CircularPSP project, CE is understood as any activity which implements environmentally preferred actions for consumers and producers aiming to optimise the value of materials and products throughout their lifecycle, while minimising waste and environmental impact and stimulate regenerative growth [15]. Such activity is often described through the 10 R-strategies hierarchically ranked by their circular impact [28], [29]. The CircularPSP CE Taxonomy has extended the 10-R concept by effective strategies documented in leading standards and established in market practice. Inspired by the framework elaborated by ECOS [30], we argue that CE-strategies can be clustered into the following four pillars with our additions marked with an asterisk:

Produce less	Use longer	Use again	Restore ecosystems
Refuse	Reuse	Cascade*	Regenerate*
Rethink	Resell*	Recycle	Use of
Reduce	Redistribute*	Recover	sustainable
(use)	Share*	Re-circulate	& toxic free
Reduce	Repair	*	materials
(by design) *	Refurbish	Remine*	
	Remanufacture		
	Repurpose		

* Additions of CircularPSP to widely used set of R-strategies.

B. Pre-commercial procurement (PCP)

PCP targets situations that require radical or transformative innovation or Research and Development (R&D) and for which there are typically no solutions on or close to the market yet. Multiple approaches to solve the problem might exist with no evidence as to which is the most effective solution to the customer’s needs. PCP simultaneously awards R&D contracts to several competing contractors at the same time, to compare different approaches to solving the problem. This provides procurers with the opportunity to compare different solutions. Innovators benefit from multiple feedback loops during R&D and gain a first customer reference.

Evaluations after each phase will progressively identify the solutions that offer the best value for money and meet the customers’ needs. This phased approach allows successful contractors to improve their offers for the next phase, based on both lessons learnt and feedback from procurers in the previous phase. The incrementally enlarging contract scope across phases facilitates Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) participation, enabling gradual business expansion.

C. CE-Taxonomy

To enable the transition to CE in an effective manner, a harmonised framework of standardised terminology and a repository of data sources, case studies, procurement criteria and upskilling materials are needed. CircularPSP has initiated an open ‘CE Taxonomy working group’ to attract wide stakeholder participation following an iterative co-development process. The open-access repository includes more than 470 categorised sources and is continuously being expanded by Suppliers, guest contributors and project partners. We continuously invite researchers and practitioners to test, use and contribute to the repository following FAIR principles. In addition, the CE Taxonomy [21] lists the preferred set of CE standards and harmonised terminologies for CE strategies also offering missing terminology, which are being applied to the CE-solutions.

III. CHALLENGE ANALYSIS

To define the common challenge, the CircularPSP consortium has conducted extensive literature review, desk research, eight open market consultations inviting cities and potentials Suppliers, a survey (25 respondents) and focus groups in each procuring municipality involving CE experts, regular staff and SME representatives (199 participants). The common challenge defines four areas of need described in summary below: A) information, B) operation, C) organisation, and D) change. The description is based on the Challenge Brief [19] reflecting insights gathered during co-design and testing of prototype CE-solutions, input received from Follower organisations and wider interaction with the community.

A. Information

Municipalities and businesses in the local economy require support in accessing, understanding and applying the growing body of highly distributed and often unorganised knowledge on CE transition which is often not available in their native language [31]. Fundamentally, the CE is lacking a common language and classifications, hindering not only the use of data but also the exchange

between stakeholders. Even if the large body of sources would be collected (i.e. through the CE Taxonomy) a human is not able to conduct targeted research across these. Organisations of all sizes fail to make use of their own data [32] and understand the way their own local economy operates or where opportunities exist to shift to circularity.

From the perspective of an individual municipal worker who has never applied circular thinking, the lack of reliable data, complexity of terminology and uncertainty of the status quo is overburdening and would have the consequence of hindering the communication towards decision makers.

B. Operation

Current municipal operation utilises decades long experience in the linear system [33]. To transition, municipalities require a vision, milestones and targets for their departments. Aside from a selected number of lighthouse cities, existing strategies and targets are often incomplete, simplified or focus solely on ‘end of pipe’ solutions [34]. For instance, many Cities begin their circular journey in the procurement department without full understanding of what CE strategies could achieve at earlier stages including during the conceptualisation, design and planning phases (or steps). Departmental staff required achieving higher ranking Circular strategies has often no knowledge and less experience in applying circular actions as part of their day-to-day tasks. Lastly, organisations lack simple and robust CE indicators to track progress and positive impact.

From the perspective of an individual, any circular action is to be considered a risk. Staff is expected to diverge from the regular path with no mission, little guidance and no means of verifying action.

C. Organisation

Only few Cities established specialised teams to implement CE transition. Strategies often only exist as complex policy papers. Other complications are legacy software not adequately reflecting circular action and the need to establish new relationships across departments and with new supplier networks. To establish these networks and to inform existing suppliers of changing procurement patterns and criteria new means of information and the ability of upskilling the local economy is required. Communication needs to be improved internally with many CE-experts stating dissatisfaction with the fact that they are involved with creating of strategies but have no means of observing what sustainable action as there is no central platform where ongoing efforts are collected. Consequently, they have also no means of being reached or step in.

From the perspective of an individual, the municipal organisation is not creating any form of transparency and is offering little to no support.

D. Change

Several studies highlight that public bodies, including municipalities, tend to be both path-dependent in showing resistance to change or implement new solutions, and risk-avoiding [35], [36]. The prevalent linear mindset among politicians [37]) and employees, and a lack or insufficiency of adequate awareness, information and expertise on CE are often the reason that public authorities encounter

considerable obstacles when attempting to transition to and implement CE concepts [38], [39], [40]. Training material on the relevant circular concepts and technologies is widely dispersed and rarely available in local language.

From the perspective of an individual – intrinsic adversity to change aside – the municipal organisation is neither justifying change sufficiently nor is it providing the necessary circular upskilling in context of day-to-day work.

IV. SOLUTIONS

The remaining two competing CE-solutions tackle the four areas of need holistically in one Public Service Platform. Several components of the platform are supported by an AI trained on CE. The CE-solution is able to integrate the varying needs enabling each party to begin or progress their circular transition journey.

The solutions are cloud-hosted with a modular architecture to ensure scalability. The AI deployed on the PSP pools publicly available CE knowledge -among others, from CircularPSP Taxonomy repository- and subsequently specialises to specific city contexts based on local data and strategy sources. The AI systems apply large language models (LLM) to generate context-specific and relevant outputs and are strengthened by a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) approach and natural language processing (NLP) to allow multilingual analyses and outputs. Suppliers have developed regularly updated AI risk assessments following the EU model contractual AI clauses to pilot AI procurements [41], addressing e.g. potential biases, inaccuracies, privacy and transparency. A similar approach is applied to cyber security and data governance.

Fig. 1. CE-solution structure

To implement the CE-solution in cities, an onboarding process with city decision makers and CE experts is initiated to co-design with Suppliers a city mission. This co-design takes place within a limited timeframe (estimated 1-3 months) in which targets and indicators are set. After onboarding, the solution is rolled out throughout the organisation for day-to-day use and users can access a mission display.

The most challenging component is to induce individual municipal workers to advance on the mission targets

through actionable workflows offering step-by-step guidance. A workflow contains a selection of standard-based modules tailored to the individual depending on expertise and upskilling need. A module contains instructions, steps and recording of intermediate results and where required upskilling material to introduce or understanding of concepts. The Supplier's CE-experts have designed a range of template workflows which will be continuously monitored for their success. Users can select from these workflows and create an issue-specific instance. Users can also generate workflows with AI-assistance following their research of case studies. Workflows can be shared with co-workers and municipal CE experts can be involved if assistance is required.

The CE-solution further provides specialised support to procurement officials. The AI is trained on CE procurement criteria and validation clauses from good practice sources as well as through searching relevant procurements using relevant taxonomies. The AI can analyse uploaded procurement packages for opportunities to further advance or improve circular requirements.

Fig. 2. Operational processes CE-solution

To facilitate long lasting change, platform users are being empowered by tailored training and learning. The platform facilitates structured communication and networking on topics like funding opportunities both within and between cities, as well as local economy actors.

Full documentation of the competing platforms will be released when the Suppliers go public.

V. TESTING AND EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

As of this PCP phase, two Suppliers develop CE-solutions, namely CircularAI and VCG.AI. Both CE-solutions are currently undergoing a second iteration of intensive prototype testing. Testing is being conducted by CircularPSP project members (Procurers), as well as by testers in departments within municipalities and municipal owned organisations (External Testers), each following tailored evaluation methods.

Starting in summer, testing will be conducted for 11 months in real-life settings. An expected number of 20 entities with direct links to the procurers will deploy the CE-solutions in their organisation beginning with a full roll-out of Supplier-supported development of City Missions which will be translated into day-to-day operations by onboarded and trained staff members. In parallel, one Supplier per site deploys a change playbook which contains onboarding,

events and wider communication efforts tailored to the City Mission and local circumstances.

Other interested cities and governmental organisations in the CircularPSP Follower Network will be invited to conduct limited testing from autumn 2025.

Fig. 3. Testing and evaluation loops

Aside of technical KPIs, the evaluation framework will encompass two dimensions: user satisfaction and systemic impact. User satisfaction will be measured through the previously described evaluation loops and includes clarity, usability and accessibility, among others. Impact will be assessed along the created mission targets, indicators and workflows, both during testing the mission creation process and after the solution implementation. Assessment criteria for mission target setting include viability, consistency and (local) relevance. After the solution implementation, impacts will be measured according to the set indicators (e.g. emission and waste reductions, share of circular procurements).

VI. CONCLUSION

To meet sustainability goals, CE principles and practices need to be adopted by ten-thousands public organisations. Many stakeholders struggle in gathering information for existing solutions, structure or implement operational action, organise internal and external data exchange needed, and shift the linear mindset of staff and within organisational hierarchies. CircularPSP offers an innovative starting point for municipalities. The CE-solutions consolidate existing and learn from future knowledge, provide step-by-step guidance building the confidence of users. The expected level of quality is high, given the extensive co-design and testing by a representative group of municipalities. A broad set of evaluation methods will be deployed during real-life testing which will open to the public. A wide-ranging uptake of the solution could lead to shifting billions of public procurements toward circular solutions starting with low hanging fruits first.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Pre-Commercial Procurement Programme, under Grant Agreement n° 101092208.

Project partners: CircularBerlin, Forum Virium Helsinki, Guimarães, Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality, ReLondon, Skupnost občin Slovenije, Sveriges Kommuner och Regioner & EEIP, empirica, Research Institutes of Sweden & CircularPSP Follower Network.

We have received valuable input from our project officers Lieve Bos and Ramón Sanmartín Sola, project reviewers Luis Eulogio Anido Rifón, José Ramón Ferri Tormo and Simone Cadeddu, as well as external experts Petra Wilson, Ilkay Kaynak, Johan Källstrand, Yildiray Kabak, Kristina Dobricic. We learned from our Suppliers Swappsi, Tübitak Bilgem, GTE Sustainability Research and Consultancy, INNCSO innovation (CircularAI); Metabolic (CIRRUS); VXT Research, Hahmota (CREVICES); Supercharge-Beyondly; VCG.AI.

DISCLAIMER

This is the Accepted Manuscript (AM) of the article accepted for publication in the Proceedings of the IEEE 21st International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT 2025). It is not the final published Version of Record (VoR), which is available in IEEE Xplore, DOI: [10.1109/DCOSS-IoT65416.2025.00081](https://doi.org/10.1109/DCOSS-IoT65416.2025.00081).

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